
AI governance around the world

Country profile: Canada

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About The Alan Turing Institute

The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence.

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About the project

Introduction

The international AI governance landscape continues to evolve as jurisdictions around the world balance the need to navigate increased competition with earlier commitments to advancing international alignment and cooperation on AI governance and safety. Many jurisdictions have recognised the strategic implications of AI, both for economic prosperity and national security, and accelerated investment in domestic AI infrastructure has begun to engender a more competitive international environment. However, the role of international trade and global cooperation remains crucial in realising the economic benefits of AI while effectively managing the technology's risks.

As high-level AI principles are translated into concrete policies and distinct regulatory frameworks, jurisdictions are managing the tensions between competitive and cooperative priorities. Meaningful progress towards effective international AI governance will require a clear and detailed understanding of how different countries are approaching AI governance in practice. Tracking primary source policy initiatives over the past decade, the *AI governance around the world* project sheds light on shifting national priorities on AI, dynamics of cooperation and competition, and potential areas of international alignment.

Project aims

The *AI governance around the world* project seeks to map this evolving landscape through a series of country profiles based on a consistent framework. Each profile provides a descriptive overview of a jurisdiction's approach to AI regulation and standardisation, highlighting the high-level aims and principles, definitions of relevant technologies, key policy initiatives and the main features of the respective standardisation systems. Drawing exclusively on primary sources, the country profiles analyse legal and policy instruments, national strategies, standardisation initiatives, and public investments that reflect the varied and evolving approaches that different jurisdictions are taking to AI governance.

This series offers a foundation for comparative analysis and future work on global regulatory interoperability without commenting on the efficacy of the specific governance models being adopted at the jurisdictional level. As more profiles are developed, the project aims to contribute to international understanding of where alignment is emerging and where deeper coordination may be needed.

Canada

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Executive summary

The Government of Canada's initial forays into AI—as illustrated by its innovation-heavy 2017 AI strategy—focused primarily on industry and innovation. However, regulation took centre stage in recent years with the release of 2022's AI and Data Act (AIDA), inspired in part by the EU AI Act. Like the EU, Canada opted for a largely horizontal approach to regulating AI, especially through the omnibus Bill C-27 which consisted of AIDA, Consumer Privacy Protection Act, and Personal Information and Data Act. Canada also has policies like the Directive on Automated Decision Making (DADM) covering broad categories of systems across all use cases. However, following the resignation of Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau and prorogation of the Canadian Parliament in early 2025, AIDA was halted in the House of Commons, and there is no indication yet if AIDA will be reintroduced under the 45th Parliamentary term.

On the standardisation front, the Standards Council of Canada has initiated a pilot program to test the domestic applicability of international standards, launched an AI and Data Governance Standardization Collaborative, and is actively participating in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42. Exactly what approach to AI standardisation the country will adopt remains to be seen, though its history of and continued interest in international alignment will likely influence its undertakings.

Key Policy Initiatives

2017 **Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy**

A strategy to recruit and retain top AI talent to enable long-term excellence in AI innovation

2019 **Digital Charter**

A principled approach to guide federal government's digital transformation

2019 **Directive on Automated Decision-Making**

A risk-based policy applicable to all ADMs deployed by the federal government

2022 **Digital Charter Implementation Act, 2022**

Also known as Bill C-27 which is now inactive

2023 **Guardrails for Generative AI – Code of Practice**

Voluntary framework with six guiding principles

2023 **Cybersecurity Generative AI guidance**

Voluntary guidance on security risks of AI

2024 **Canadian AI Safety Institute**

Part of the Canadian government's plan to advance safe and responsible AI.

Regulatory approach to AI

High-level aims and principles

The Government of Canada's initial interest in AI was firmly in the innovation camp, investing CAD 125M and CAD 443M (approximately GBP 75M and GBP 257M) in 2017 and 2021, respectively, into commercialisation, research, and skills training.¹ These areas of focus, in addition to standards, make up the central pillars of the Pan-Canadian AI Strategy.²

Two years into the launch of the strategy, Canada's Digital Charter was announced which sets out ten principles to guide the federal government's digital transformation efforts. As such, in the years following the strategy's launch, the federal government has increasingly championed responsible AI governance, embracing a dual innovation-trustworthiness approach and publishing principles for government uses of AI.³ In line with, but narrower in scope than the OECD's, which Canada adopted in 2019,⁴ these principles cover AI measurement, transparency, recourse, privacy, and user training.

In 2022, Digital Charter Implementation Act, i.e. Bill C-27, was introduced in the Parliament. Bill C-27 proposed three legislations: Consumer Privacy Protection Act, AIDA, and Personal Information and Data Protection Tribunal Act. Additionally, Canada also has a Directive on Automated Decision Making (DADM) which governs the government's use of AI through a risk-based approach. Keeping with advancements in technology, in 2023, the Canadian government also published a guide on the use of generative AI as well as a code of practice. Moreover, the same year, key industry actors also committed to a Voluntary Code of Conduct on the Responsible Development and Management of Advanced Generative AI Systems.

¹ Invest in Canada, 'Pan-Canadian AI Strategy', Invest in Canada, accessed 27 March 2023, <https://www.investcanada.ca/programs-incentives/pan-canadian-ai-strategy>; Science and Economic Development Canada Innovation, 'Government of Canada Launches Second Phase of the Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy', news releases, 22 June 2022, <https://www.canada.ca/en/innovation-science-economic-development/news/2022/06/government-of-canada-launches-second-phase-of-the-pan-canadian-artificial-intelligence-strategy.html>.

² Canadian government, 'Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy'.

³ Treasury Board of Canada Secretariat, 'Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)', 22 November 2018, <https://www.canada.ca/en/government/system/digital-government/digital-government-innovations/responsible-use-ai.html>.

⁴ OECD, 'Forty-Two Countries Adopt New OECD Principles on Artificial Intelligence - OECD', 25 May 2019, <https://www.oecd.org/science/forty-two-countries-adopt-new-oecd-principles-on-artificial-intelligence.htm>.

The government of Canada has also made some efforts to capture public opinion, launching public consultations in 2021 and 2023 on how to amend the Copyright Act to account for AI and generative AI, respectively.⁵ ⁶ The government did not hold public consultations on AIDA,⁷ instead opting to conduct hundreds of engagements with predominantly industry stakeholders more than a year after it was originally released.

Definitions of relevant technologies

DADM characterises AI as “information technology that performs tasks that would ordinarily require biological brainpower to accomplish, such as making sense of spoken language, learning behaviours, or solving problems”.⁸ It should be noted that some tasks requiring brainpower (e.g., complex calculations) can be accomplished by a traditional computer.

DADM applies to any “automated decision system”, that is, “any technology that either assists or replaces the judgement of human decision-makers. These systems draw from fields like statistics, linguistics, and computer science, and use techniques such as rules-based systems, regression, predictive analytics, machine learning, deep learning, and neural nets”.⁹ Note that some AI systems—e.g., non-decision-making generative AI—are not covered by this definition.

Key policy initiatives

Canada’s regulatory initiatives can be classed along two axes: voluntary or binding, and government-aimed or industry-aimed. The AI and Data Act, which would have been the country’s flagship AI legislation, was an example of AI regulation that would impose legally binding requirements on commercial developers and users.¹⁰ Meanwhile, the

⁵ Science and Economic Development Canada Innovation, ‘The Government of Canada Launches Consultation on a Modern Copyright Framework for AI and the Internet of Things’, news releases, 16 July 2021, <https://www.canada.ca/en/innovation-science-economic-development/news/2021/07/the-government-of-canada-launches-consultation-on-a-modern-copyright-framework-for-ai-and-the-internet-of-things.html>.

⁶ Government of Canada, ‘Consultation Paper: Consultation on Copyright in the Age of Generative Artificial Intelligence’, 1 December 2023, <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/strategic-policy-sector/en/marketplace-framework-policy/consultation-paper-consultation-copyright-age-generative-artificial-intelligence>.

⁷ Teresa Scassa, ‘Explaining the AI and Data Act’, Teresa Scassa, 21 March 2023, https://www.teresascassa.ca/index.php?option=com_k2&view=item&id=369:explaining-the-ai-and-data-act&Itemid=80.

⁸ Government of Canada, ‘Directive on Automated Decision Making’.

⁹ Government of Canada.

¹⁰ Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry, C-27: An Act to enact the Consumer Privacy Protection Act, the Personal Information and Data Protection Tribunal Act and the Artificial Intelligence and Data Act and to make consequential and related amendments to other Acts.

Directive on Automated Decision Making imposes binding requirements on government entities.¹¹ On the other hand, guidance issued by the government on the use of generative AI, both government-aimed,¹² and industry-aimed¹³ are voluntary in nature.

While all Canadian initiatives have so far been largely horizontal in scope, many – notably the Directive on Automated Decision Making and the government’s numerous generative AI guides – target only a specific type of system.

AI and Data Act

The AI and Data Act (AIDA) would have been Canada’s central piece of AI legislation. It was introduced in Bill C-27 alongside two data acts, all intended to modernise the country’s data and technology laws.¹⁴ Drafted by Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada (ISED), AIDA would have established requirements for the design, development, and use of AI systems (excluding national security systems) during interprovincial or international commerce.¹⁵

Like the EU AI Act, AIDA proposed a risk-based approach, though it used “high-impact” language instead of “high-risk”.¹⁶ However, unlike the EU AI Act, AIDA did not have a category of prohibited uses, and would have applied only to uses that were classified as “high-impact”. The bill itself was very short and made numerous references to regulation that did not yet exist, and left room for new provincial or federal regulation. For instance, a high-impact system was defined as meeting “the criteria for a high-impact system that are established in regulations”.¹⁷

¹¹ Government of Canada, ‘Directive on Automated Decision Making’.

¹² Government of Canada, ‘Guide on the Use of Generative AI’, Government of Canada, 6 September 2023, <https://www.canada.ca/en/government/system/digital-government/digital-government-innovations/responsible-use-ai/guide-use-generative-ai.html>.

¹³ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, ‘Canadian Guardrails for Generative AI – Code of Practice’, Government of Canada, 16 August 2023, <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/ised/en/consultation-development-canadian-code-practice-generative-artificial-intelligence-systems/canadian-guardrails-generative-ai-code-practice>; Government of Canada, ‘Voluntary Code of Conduct on the Responsible Development and Management of Advanced Generative AI Systems’, 28 September 2023, <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/ised/en/voluntary-code-conduct-responsible-development-and-management-advanced-generative-ai-systems>; Canadian Centre for Cyber Security, ‘Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) - ITSAP.00.041’, Government of Canada, 14 July 2023, <https://www.cyber.gc.ca/en/guidance/generative-artificial-intelligence-ai-itsap00041>.

¹⁴ Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry, C-27: An Act to enact the Consumer Privacy Protection Act, the Personal Information and Data Protection Tribunal Act and the Artificial Intelligence and Data Act and to make consequential and related amendments to other Acts.

¹⁵ Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry, sec. 39(3-4).

¹⁶ Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry, sec. 39(5).

¹⁷ Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry, sec. 39(5).

In November 2023, the Minister of Innovation, Science, and Industry proposed a series of substantial amendments to the bill.¹⁸ These included switching the bill's definition of AI to one based on the OECD's and introducing definitions for machine learning and general-purpose systems. The amendments laid out several requirements for any developers of general-purpose systems, including the production of an accountability framework describing roles, responsibilities, policies, and other key information pertaining to the management of the system. Seven initial categories of high-impact systems were also described, including law enforcement systems and systems that make "employment-related decisions".

AIDA was criticised throughout its lifetime for numerous reasons, such as concerns regarding the requirements for developers and operators of high-risk AI systems being too vague and lack of inclusion in the stakeholder review of the bill. AIDA is now inactive.

Canadian AI Safety Institute

A major development at the AI Seoul Summit was the announcement of the International Network of AI Safety Institutes, with Canada as one of the founding members.¹⁹ The inaugural convening of the Canadian AI Safety Institute (CAISI) took place in November 2024 with the goal to advance AI safety through international collaborations and to ensure global governments are well-positioned to respond to the risks of advanced AI systems. CAISI is led by ISED. The research carried out at CAISI is supported by the National Research Council of Canada as well as the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research.

Canadian Guardrails for Generative AI – Code of Practice

In its code of practice for generative AI, released in August 2023, the Government of Canada asserted its intent to "prioritize the regulation of generative AI systems should AIDA receive royal assent".²⁰ The code of practice, it explained, would serve as voluntary guidance in the interim. The code lays out six ethical principles that organisations should strive to uphold: fairness and equity, human oversight and monitoring, validity and robustness, accountability, safety (with a particular focus on preventing malicious or inappropriate use), and transparency (developers and deployers are encouraged to share "meaningful" explanations of the system's development process and to provide a "reliable and freely available method", such as

¹⁸ François-Philippe Champagne, 'Letter from Minister of Innovation, Science, and Industry', 28 November 2023.

¹⁹ "Canadian Artificial Intelligence Safety Institute." Government of Canada. November 12, 2024. <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/ised/en/canadian-artificial-intelligence-safety-institute>.

²⁰ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 'Canadian Guardrails for Generative AI – Code of Practice'.

watermarking, to make it easier for users to identify AI-generated content – though no practical or technical guidance is given).²¹ The Government requested feedback from the public on its choice of principles, as well as on whether its recommendations are sufficient to ensure that AI systems are both trusted and trustworthy. The Government did not, however, hold any public consultations, only a series of invite-only roundtables.

Voluntary Code of Conduct on the Responsible Development and Management of Advanced Generative AI Systems

The document resulting from the above consultation was a voluntary code of conduct for “firms developing or managing the operations of a generative AI system with general-purpose capabilities”.²² Early signatories to the code include Canadian AI research institutes and telecoms companies; other organisations, however, have expressed hesitation, with some even arguing against any perceived form of regulatory oversight.²³

The code lays out the same high-level principles as its predecessor and provides additional high-level information on the activities firms should undertake in order to satisfy each principle.²⁴ For example, under the accountability principle, the code expects signatories to establish comprehensive risk management systems and to share best practices for risk management with other firms. In addition to its principle-specific provisions, the code requires that “signatories also commit to support[ing] the ongoing development of a robust, responsible AI ecosystem in Canada”, including by “contributing to the development and application of standards”. The prioritisation of “human rights, accessibility, and environmental sustainability” in the development and deployment process is also emphasised.

A few obligations from the previous code of practice have been removed from the code of conduct, most notably the requirement that developers and deployers “provide a meaningful explanation of the process used to develop the system”.²⁵ The new code only specifies that a firm releases information about the types of training data used and any risk mitigation steps taken.²⁶

²¹ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada.

²² Government of Canada, ‘Voluntary Code of Conduct on the Responsible Development and Management of Advanced Generative AI Systems’.

²³ Government of Canada.

²⁴ Government of Canada.

²⁵ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, ‘Canadian Guardrails for Generative AI – Code of Practice’.

²⁶ Government of Canada, ‘Voluntary Code of Conduct on the Responsible Development and Management of Advanced Generative AI Systems’.

Neither document makes any reference to issues of copyright or worker exploitation, nor recommends that firms implement redress mechanisms or provide public or user education on the limitations and risks of AI systems.

Directive on Automated Decision Making

Enacted in 2019, the Treasury Board's DADM applies to all automated decision systems deployed by the federal government (excluding national security systems).²⁷ It requires the completion of an algorithmic impact assessment prior to development and after any functionality or scope change, with further requirements determined by the assessment's results, which must also be published online.²⁸ The Directive mandates numerous transparency and quality assurance requirements, including providing explanations and testing for bias.²⁹

Guide on the use of Generative AI

In September 2023, the federal government issued guidance for public servants on how to ensure that their use of generative AI aligns with what it calls the 'FASTER' principles: fairness, accountability, security, transparency, education (meaning that the user understands the tool's limitations and use and can critically assess its outputs), and relevance to the present task.³⁰ The guidance discusses the applicability – or in many cases lack of applicability – of the DADM to generative AI: since the terms of service of ChatGPT and similar tools preclude them from being used to make high-impact decisions, many government uses of the technology would fall outside of the DADM's scope. The guidance also explores the impact of existing privacy laws on generative AI; for example, the Privacy Act would require that any new personal data generated by an AI system be checked for accuracy, relevance, and completeness and not be used for any purpose other than the one for which it was originally generated.

The guidelines identify various areas of concern and corresponding best practices. These include security and privacy concerns if inputted data is collected by AI developers for further training or other uses; the generation of biased or inaccurate content – particularly salient if the government could be held liable for discrimination or other harm caused; the potential for employees to become overly dependent on the technology; the environmental impact of large AI systems; and the risk of deception if the public is not informed that they are interacting with or consuming AI-generated content. Recommended solutions involve thoughtfully engaging with – or not engaging with, when its use is not deemed appropriate – a system and its outputs, as well as

²⁷ Government of Canada, 'Directive on Automated Decision Making', sec. 5.

²⁸ Government of Canada, sec. 6.1.

²⁹ Government of Canada, sec. 6.2-6.3.

³⁰ Government of Canada, 'Guide on the Use of Generative AI'.

clearly signposting when external communications are AI-generated. Notably, while the guidance raises the possibility that the collection of online content to train generative AI systems may violate intellectual property or privacy rights, it does not make any definitive statements about the legality of such practices.

Canadian Centre for Cyber Security's generative artificial intelligence guidance

The Canadian Centre for Cyber Security, which sits within the Communications Security Establishment (Canada's national cryptologic agency) published guidance on the security risks of AI.³¹ Aimed at Canadian organisations, the guidance touches both on risks that affect developers (e.g., attacks that inject poisoned data into training sets) and risks that affect users (e.g., data leaks from including sensitive information in chatbot queries), as well as on ones that stem from the malicious use of generative AI systems (e.g., widespread, highly targeted phishing attacks). Steps organisations can take to protect against generative AI fuelled cyber-attacks are discussed, as are recommended security protections for when organisations engage with generative AI systems themselves.

Pan-Canadian AI Strategy

Launched in 2017 and renewed and expanded in 2021, the Pan-Canadian AI Strategy was the world's first national AI strategy.³² Spearheaded by ISED and led and developed by the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research (CIFAR), the strategy has three pillars: commercialisation, standards, and talent and research. The National AI Institutes—three research hubs located in Montreal, Toronto, and Edmonton—play a central role in pillars 1 and 3, both producing research and adapting it for commercial use.³³

Advisory Council on AI

Made up of members from industry, civil society, academia, and government, the Advisory Council advises ISED on AI governance and economic growth.³⁴ Its two working groups on public awareness and commercialisation produce reports and

³¹ Canadian Centre for Cyber Security, 'Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) - ITSAP.00.041'.

³² Innovation, 'Government of Canada Launches Second Phase of the Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy'; CIFAR, 'Pan-Canadian AI Strategy', CIFAR, accessed 27 March 2023, <https://cifar.ca/ai/>.

³³ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 'Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy - Home' (Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 20 July 2022), <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/ai-strategy/en/pan-canadian-artificial-intelligence-strategy>.

³⁴ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 'Advisory Council on Artificial Intelligence', accessed 1 March 2023, <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/advisory-council-artificial-intelligence/en/advisory-council-artificial-intelligence>.

recommendations, with the former working—through surveys and workshops—to assess and advance public awareness of AI ethics.³⁵

The Global Partnership on AI (GPAI)

GPAI brings 29 countries together to coordinate around issues of responsible AI,³⁶ data governance, the future of work, and innovation and commercialisation.³⁷ Canada has held a central position in GPAI since its inception in 2020, chairing the initiative in 2021 and hosting one of its two centres of expertise—the International Centre of Expertise in Montreal on Artificial Intelligence (CEIMIA).³⁸

³⁵ Government of Canada, 'Learning Together for Responsible Artificial Intelligence: Report of the Public Awareness Working Group', Government of Canada (Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 3 March 2023), <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/advisory-council-artificial-intelligence/en/public-awareness-working-group/learning-together-responsible-artificial-intelligence>; Innovation Government of Canada, 'Commercialization Working Group Final Report February 2020', Government of Canada, 6 November 2020, <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/advisory-council-artificial-intelligence/en/commercialization-working-group/commercialization-working-group-final-report-february-2020>.

³⁶ GPAI, 'Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence - GPAI', GPAI, accessed 27 March 2023, <https://gpai.ai/>.

³⁷ GPAI, 'About GPAI', GPAI, accessed 27 March 2023, <https://gpai.ai/about/>.

³⁸ Science and Economic Development Canada Innovation, 'Minister Champagne Presents Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence Priorities for 2021', Government of Canada, 30 June 2021, <https://www.canada.ca/en/innovation-science-economic-development/news/2021/06/minister-champagne-presents-global-partnership-on-artificial-intelligence-priorities-for-2021.html>; GPAI, 'About GPAI'.

Approach to AI Standardisation

Main features of the standardisation system

Canada's main standards organisation is the Standards Council of Canada (SCC). As a crown corporation, the SCC operates with full independence but reports to, receives partial funding from, and is wholly owned by ISED.³⁹

The SCC does not develop standards but instead coordinates standardisation work across the country, accrediting SDOs and conformity assessment organisations (over 400 as of 2023), supporting organisations in getting involved with standardisation at the national and international level, and approving national standards.⁴⁰

Following a 1964 government review of standardisation activities that highlighted a lack of coordination and long-term planning, industry and government support, and international involvement, the SCC was established by the Parliament in 1970.⁴¹ Today, the SCC covers all major areas of standardisation, with flagship initiatives ranging in focus from cybersecurity to cannabis.⁴²

National standards of Canada are by default voluntary but can be made mandatory if referenced in legislation or regulation.⁴³ To ensure alignment with regulatory objectives, federal, provincial, and territorial governments take an active interest in standardisation.⁴⁴

³⁹ Standards Council of Canada, 'What Is the SCC?', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 7 March 2012, <https://www.scc.ca/en/faq-what-is-the-standards-council-of-canada>.

⁴⁰ Standards Council of Canada; International Trade Administration, 'Canada - Country Commercial Guide', International Trade Administration, 8 March 2022, <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/canada-standards-trade>.

⁴¹ Standards Council of Canada, 'History', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 7 March 2012, <https://www.scc.ca/en/about-scc/history>.

⁴² 'Flagship Initiatives', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 31 January 2019, <https://www.scc.ca/en/flagships>.

⁴³ Standards Council of Canada, 'Types of Standards', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 13 February 2019, <https://www.scc.ca/en/types-standards>.

⁴⁴ Standards Council of Canada, 'How Regulators Can Get Involved', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 3 May 2012, <https://www.scc.ca/en/stakeholder-participation/government/participate>.

The government's Canadian General Standards Board sets up and oversees standards committees, which have collectively produced over 350 standards.⁴⁵ The government also publishes reports and roadmaps, including a 2021 Transport Canada roadmap for international standardisation.⁴⁶

The SCC, for its part, encourages government involvement in standardisation, highlighting regulatory ease, consumer protection, and competitiveness and innovation boosting as key benefits to standardisation.⁴⁷

An ISO member since 1972,⁴⁸ the SCC serves as Secretariat for 18 committees.⁴⁹

National AI-focused standardisation activities

While the SCC has yet to approve any AI-related standards as national standards, the Canadian government is positioning AI standards as vital tools, earmarking CAD 8.6M (GBD 5M) in its AI strategy for their development and adoption.⁵⁰

The SCC's Data Governance Standardization Collaborative published a roadmap in 2021, laying out recommendations relating to 35 issues, including AI explainability, bias, and performance. The roadmap discusses what kinds of standards are needed and how they might fit with regulation.⁵¹ The Transport Canada roadmap likewise asserted the importance of AI standards, proposing the establishment of a multi-stakeholder collaborative to identify gaps in the AI standardisation landscape, develop standardisation strategies, and determine how to utilise international standards.⁵²

⁴⁵ Canadian General Standards Board, 'Standards Development', Government of Canada, accessed 27 March 2023, <https://www.tpsgc-pwgsc.gc.ca/ongc-cgsb/programme-program/normes-standards/index-eng.html>.

⁴⁶ Transport Canada, 'International Standards: Targeted Regulatory ReviewRegulatory Roadmap', accessed 1 March 2023, <https://tc.canada.ca/en/corporate-services/acts-regulations/international-standards-targeted-regulatory-review-regulatory-roadmap>.

⁴⁷ Standards Council of Canada, 'Benefits of Standardization for Government', Standards Council of Canada - Conseil canadien des normes, 7 March 2012, <https://www.scc.ca/en/information-for/government/benefits>.

⁴⁸ Standards Council of Canada, "History of SCC." SCC, Accessed June 30, 2025. <https://www.jtc1sc34.org/en/about-scc/history.html>.

⁴⁹ Standards Council of Canada, "What We Do." SCC, Accessed June 30, 2025. <https://scc-ccn.ca/about-us/what-we-do>.

⁵⁰ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, 'Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy - Home'.

⁵¹ Standards Council of Canada, 'Canadian Data Governance Standardization Roadmap', 28 June 2021, https://www.scc.ca/en/system/files/publications/SCC_Data_Gov_Roadmap_EN.pdf.

⁵² Transport Canada, 'International Standards'.

In March 2023, the scope of the Data Governance Standardization Collaborative was expanded to officially include AI.⁵³ The newly dubbed AI and Data Governance Standardization Collaborative's work will build off of its 2021 roadmap, as well as off of a 2023 white paper produced by the University of Toronto's Schwartz Reisman Institute for Technology and Society.⁵⁴ The white paper lays out several recommendations and goals, including the increased participation of Canadians and Canadian companies (particularly SMEs) in the international standards development process and the prioritisation of Indigenous voices. The white paper also puts forward three criteria for determining which AI use cases should be prioritised for standardisation: 1) if the use case is singled out by existing regulation or legislation; 2) if the use case "involves technical components of trustworthy AI that could help unlock research, innovation, or commercialization in an industry that is important to Canada or the public interest" (the aim here is to "use such applications as proxies to identify AI uses about which the public might have heightened reticence"); and 3) if the use case "represents a sector with recognized Canadian leadership" (here, the ultimate goal is to ensure that "standards are aligned with [Canada's] values and commercial interests"). Areas that meet all three criteria include regulatory technology, credit scoring, and climate change.

The SCC's most concrete AI standardisation work to date involves an accreditation pilot for AI management systems, launched in 2022 in partnership with ISED, and completed in 2023.⁵⁵ The project involves a conformity assessment body testing an AI system against ISO 42001, the government's Algorithmic Impact Assessment, and the Responsible AI Institute's certification scheme, with more conformity assessors and AI users added in 2024. The pilot showcases the SCC's interest in testing the applicability of international standards to a Canadian context, as well as investigating (by applying both the government's and the Responsible AI Institute's assessments, which include system-level components) the limitations of a purely management-based approach for achieving responsible AI. The Schwartz Reisman's white paper proposes as a next step a Canada-EU collaboration to expand ISO 42001 to include both a management system certification scheme and a product certification scheme.⁵⁶

It is not yet known to what extent Canada will adopt international AI standards wholesale, adapt them to suit its needs, or develop entirely new standards. Similarly, the relative importance of horizontal with respect to vertical standards has yet to be

⁵³ Standards Council of Canada, 'AI and Data Governance'.

⁵⁴ Schwartz Reisman Institute for Technology and Society and Standards Council of Canada, 'Discerning Signal from Noise: The State of Global AI Standardization and What It Means for Canada', 29 March 2023, <https://www.scc.ca/en/news-events/news/2023/white-paper-state-global-ai-standardization-and-what-it-means-for-canada>.

⁵⁵ Standards Council of Canada, 'SCC Launches Accreditation Pilot for AI Management Systems'.

⁵⁶ Schwartz Reisman Institute for Technology and Society and Standards Council of Canada, 'Discerning Signal from Noise: The State of Global AI Standardization and What It Means for Canada'.

determined. Moreover, the Schwartz Reisman white paper stresses the need to identify priority verticals for standardisation.⁵⁷

Engagement in international AI standardisation

The SCC is an active member of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42⁵⁸ and played a “pivotal role” in developing ISO/IEC 42001.⁵⁹ Given the SCC’s long history of adopting international standards, it is unsurprising that that alignment has carried over into AI. Indeed, a stated motivation of the standardisation collaborative was stakeholders’ desire for internationally aligned requirements.⁶⁰ SCC has played an important role in coordinating between different national standardisation efforts around the world.

The Schwartz Reisman white paper likewise discusses the importance of bilateral activities.⁶¹ In addition to the aforementioned joint certification scheme, a partnership with the US’s National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) is suggested, with the aims of testing the applicability of NIST’s Risk Management Framework and of mapping its similarities to ISO 42001.

⁵⁷ Schwartz Reisman Institute for Technology and Society and Standards Council of Canada.

⁵⁸ ISO, ‘ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 - Artificial Intelligence Participation’.

⁵⁹ Standards Council of Canada, ‘First International Standard for AI Management Systems Has Been Published’, Standards Council of Canada, 9 January 2024, <https://www.scc.ca/en/news-events/news/2024/first-international-standard-for-ai-management-systems-has-been-published>.

⁶⁰ Transport Canada, ‘International Standards’.

⁶¹ Schwartz Reisman Institute for Technology and Society and Standards Council of Canada, ‘Discerning Signal from Noise: The State of Global AI Standardization and What It Means for Canada’.

